

GREENGAGE

ENGAGING CITIZENS - MOBILIZING TECHNOLOGY - DELIVERING GREEN DEAL

User Evaluation Report

Work Package 6, Deliverable D6.4

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User Evaluation Reports

Work package 6, Deliverable D6.4

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List of Acronyms

UCD	User-Centered Design
GEOSS	Global Earth Observation System of Systems
EBLN	East Bristol Livable Neighbourhood
CO	Citizen Observatory

Glossary

Citizen Observatory	According to the EU project WeObserve, “Citizen Observatories (COs) are community-based environmental monitoring and information systems, that invite individuals to share observations, typically via mobile phone or the web. Throughout these activities citizens become able to participate in environmental management/local governance.”
Outcome	The expected effects, over the medium term, of projects supported under a given topic. The results of a project should contribute to these outcomes, fostered in particular by the dissemination and exploitation measures. This may include the uptake, diffusion, deployment, and/or use of the project’s results by direct target groups. Outcomes generally occur during or shortly after the end of the project. ¹
Impact	Wider long-term effects on society (including the environment), the economy and science, enabled by the outcomes of R&I investments (long term). It refers to the specific contribution of the project to the work programme expected impacts described in the destination. Impacts generally occur sometime after the end of the project. ¹
Results	What is generated during the project implementation. This may include, for example, know-how, innovative solutions, algorithms, proof of feasibility, new business models, policy recommendations, guidelines, prototypes, demonstrators, databases and datasets, trained researchers, new infrastructures, networks, etc. Most project results (inventions, scientific works, etc.) are ‘Intellectual Property’, which may, if appropriate, be protected by formal ‘Intellectual Property Rights’. ¹
Marginalized groups	“Different groups of people within a given culture, context and history at risk of being subjected to multiple discrimination due to the interplay of different personal characteristics or grounds, such as sex, gender, age, ethnicity, religion or belief, health status, disability, sexual orientation, gender identity, education or income, or living in various geographic localities” (European Institute of Gender Equality) ²
Citizen Science	“In Citizen Science, a broad network of people collaborates. Participants provide experimental data and facilities for researchers, raise new questions and co-create a new scientific culture. While they add value, volunteers acquire new learning and skills and gain a deeper understanding of the scientific work in appealing ways. As a result of this open, networked and transdisciplinary scenario, science-society-policy interactions are improved, leading in turn to a more democratic research,

¹ https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/docs/2021-2027/experts/standard-briefing-slides-for-experts_he_en.pdf

² <https://eige.europa.eu/publications-resources/thesaurus/terms/1175>

	based on evidence and informed decision-making" (Socientize consortium, 2014, p. 10).
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Executive summary (publishable)

This report presents the GREENGAGE User Evaluation report. During the GREENGAGE project, continuous user evaluation has been conducted, starting from the design phase with a User Centric Design (UCD) for the developed assets of the GREEN Engine as well as the entire data and process workflow, while performing experiments within Citizen Observatories .

This report provides details about the UCD and the evaluation framework and procedure. Furthermore, it focuses on the results from a questionnaire assessing usability and satisfaction in different pilot regions with users of the GREEN Engine toolbox and the GREENGAGE method. In the end, the report presents conclusions and important lessons learnt during the evaluation conducted in the project. The Annex contains the questionnaire used, in English.

Related documents

All GREENGAGE deliverables that are related to this document are listed below and are available at the GREENGAGE website <https://www.GREENGAGE-project.eu/knowledge-base/deliverables/> .

Deliverable D6.2 Evaluation and Impact Assessment Methodology and Design v2

Deliverable D6.6 Impact Assessment Report 2

Deliverable D6.8 GREENGAGE based Citizen Observatory White Book for PAs v2

Deliverable D4.5 GREEN Engine and manual 3

1 GREENGAGE summary

GREENGAGE , a pan-European Innovation Action, funded under the Horizon Europe Framework Programme, aimed to promote innovative governance processes, and worked to help public authorities in shaping their climate mitigation and adaptation policies. To achieve this aim, the project leveraged citizens’ participation and equipped them with innovative digital solutions that shall transform citizen’s engagement and cities’ effectiveness in delivering the European Green Deal objectives for carbon neutral cities.

Focusing on mobility, air quality and healthy living, the aim was to inspire citizens to observe and co-create their cities by sensing their urban environments. The idea was to complement, validate, and enrich information in authoritative data held by the public administrations and public agencies. This was facilitated by engaging with citizens to co-create green initiatives and to develop Citizen Observatories (CO). In GREENGAGE , Citizen Observatories were and are a place where pilot cities co-examine environmental issues integrating novel bottom-up processes with top-down perspectives. This provides the basis to co-create and co-design innovative solutions to monitor environmental problems at ground level with the help of citizens.

With two interrelated project dimensions, the project aimed to enhance intelligence applied to city decision-making processes and governance by engaging with citizen observations integrated with Copernicus, Global Earth Observation System of Systems GEOSS, in-situ, and socio-economic intelligence, and by delivering innovative governance models based on novel toolboxes of decision-making methodologies and technologies.

The Citizens Observatory campaigns were deployed and fully demonstrated in 5 pilot engagements in selected European cities and regions including: Bristol (the United Kingdom), Copenhagen (Denmark), Turano Valley (Italy), Gerace (Italy) and the region of North Brabant (the Netherlands). These innovation pilots aimed to highlight the need for smart city governance by promoting citizen engagement, co-creation, as well as gathering new data which should complement existing datasets and evidence-based decision and policymaking.

Figure 1: Structure of project GREENGAGE .

2 Object of the Deliverable

This Deliverable depicts a User Evaluation Report for the development and usage of the GREEN Engine tools based on the experiences of CO teams, public authorities', city partners (pilot owners) and city stakeholders, who provided feedback on the suitability, usability, and relevance of the tools. The evaluation was performed from month 8 to month 36 of the project to improve the tools for and during the piloting phase of the GREENGAGE project. The deliverable also provides recommendations and an outlook for further use and development of the GREEN Engine tools.

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3 Introduction

The purpose of Task T6.3, in WP6 Evaluation and Continuous Impact Assessment, was to conduct early and ongoing user evaluations to identify potential complications in the Citizen Observatory process and improve the usability and relevance of GREENGAGE software products. These evaluations aimed to ensure that the platform met the needs of diverse stakeholders, including citizens, city authorities, and observatory teams.

The tools integrated into the GREEN Engine, combined to enable the interoperable data workflow of the GREENGAGE approach, are mainly developed by entities outside the project. However, the project has also created new tools based on previous developments. For GREENGAGE, these applications have been either integrated, such as the MODE Library, or redesigned, as the GREENGAGE App based on the HotCity App, to meet the project's needs. A User Centred Design approach was employed for this process, which will be explained in section 4 of this deliverable. An ongoing evaluation process focusing on usability, suitability, relevance, effectiveness, potential benefits, and shortcomings of GREENGAGE methods and tools was conducted to enhance them. Section 5 describes the method used, and section 6 presents survey results. It should be noted that many improvements could be made through internal, in-depth testing and discussions during regular weekly meetings with developers, internal testers, and users (pilot owners). To document and manage this process, plan.io was used (see ANNEX A).

4 User Centric Design

4.1 How to perform a UCD

User-Centric Design (UCD) is a design philosophy and process that focuses on creating products, systems, or services by prioritizing the needs, preferences, and limitations of the end users throughout the entire development cycle³.

Key Principles of a UCD:

- **User Involvement from Start to Finish:** Users are engaged early in the design process and continuously consulted during development to ensure the product meets their expectations.
- **Iterative Process:** The design is refined through repeated cycles of prototyping, testing, and feedback until usability and satisfaction goals are achieved.
- **Context of Use:** The design considers the environment, tasks, and conditions under which users will interact with the product.
- **Usability Goals:** Focus on making the product effective, efficient, and satisfying for the intended users.

User-Centered Design

Figure 2: UCD process scheme, adapted from ALL TIME DESIGN⁴.

4.2 What was done in GREENGAGE

Within GREENGAGE, the UCD was mainly used to develop the GREENGAGE App based on the experiences from the HotCity App (Wernbacher et al., 2022). We started in the very early stages of the project with an intensive exploration phase, to investigate the needs of the different pilots. This was mainly done using plan.io⁵ controlled by AIT, to collect all the demanded features and their priorities.

³ <https://alltimedesign.com/a-complete-guide-to-user-centered-design-process/>

⁴ Ibid

⁵ <https://plan.io/>

#	OWNER	TRACKER	POTENTIAL TECHNOLOGIES	STATUS	PRIORITY	SUBJECT	ASSIGNEE	UPDATED
708	Brabant	Use case	Digital Twin (BUAS), HotCity, MODE, MindEarth	New	Low	Facilitate sustainable transport in areas of mobility poverty		2024-10-25 02:24 PM
754	Turano	Use case	HOPI, HotCity, MindEarth, UrbanTEP	Accepted (time needed?)	Normal	Participatory environmental monitoring		2024-05-07 11:42 AM
581	Gerace	Use case	HotCity, MindEarth, UrbanTEP	Accepted (time needed?)	Normal	Analyse citizens' usage of public spaces and determine attractiveness of public spaces.		2024-10-15 05:13 AM
580	Turano	Use case	HotCity, MindEarth, UrbanTEP	Accepted (time needed?)	Normal	Analyse citizens' usage of public spaces and determine attractiveness of public spaces.		2024-04-16 02:51 PM
578	Turano	Use case	HOPI, HotCity, MODE, MindEarth, UrbanTEP	Accepted (time needed?)	Normal	Mobility pattern analysis to determine accessibility to shops, schools, services and other local amenities		2024-04-16 02:53 PM

Figure 3: Example screenshot of the feature collection on plan.io (Screenshot © GREENGAGE).

Based on this analysis of the needs the back-end and front-end, the developer of the GREENGAGE App developed a very first mockup of the UI/UX. Figma, as a web-based design and prototyping tool that is primarily used for UI/UX design was used to collaborate on the proposed design. This enabled to elaborate the user experience at an early stage of the design.

Figure 4: Figma GREENGAGE App first UI Mockup (Screenshot © GREENGAGE).

Based on the feedback provided by potential users of the app (Pilot Owners, Citizens, project partners etc.) the developer started to create the first prototype. After an internal testing phase, the prototype was used in a first Citizen Observer experiment (April 2024) in North Brabant. At the end of this first broader usage campaign of the App, its onboarding and data analysis process, user feedback was collected through an online survey. The feedback from the survey as well as live discussions with app-users were used to further develop the app. Additionally, the entire workflow starting from onboarding, training, and usage was evaluated. This process has been performed several times throughout the entire project.

Another iterative development took place in the administration tool for the GREENGAGE app, which was provided to Observatory Owners. Initially conceived as a decentralized architecture, it quickly became evident that the application required a clearer separation of responsibilities. After completing an initial

test run in North Brabant, the collected feedback served as the basis for rebuilding the system into a centralized administration tool that is now significantly more user-friendly and efficient. In particular, weekly meetings were used to gather feedback from the pilot owners and to translate it into targeted improvements.

Another UCD development was performed for the *data quality dashboard* which is described in the following:

As part of the participatory design process for the *data quality dashboard*, we conducted user studies with non-expert users to assess the tool's effectiveness and usability. The evaluation employed a task-based approach, asking participants to perform specific tasks such as identifying faults in the data, detecting patterns, and recognizing outliers. This was complemented by qualitative feedback gathered through interviews to understand user satisfaction, perceived challenges, and suggestions for improvement. The evaluation revealed that non-expert participants highlighted several areas for improvement, particularly emphasizing the need for greater visual clarity in the visualizations and more detailed explanations regarding the purpose and usage of each visualization module. Specifically, concerns were raised about the clarity of individual modules, their presentation, and the labeling within the tool's dashboard. Based on this feedback, improvements were implemented to address these concerns, including enhanced visual separation of modules, clear titles for each module, and detailed descriptions explaining their functionality (Figure 6). This iterative refinement process demonstrates the value of participatory design in making data visualization tools more accessible and user-friendly for individuals without domain expertise.

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Figure 5: Comparison of the data quality dashboard before (top) and after (bottom) improvements⁶. (Screenshot © GREENGAGE).

5 Evaluation framework

This section provides an overview of the evaluation framework and process performed to evaluate the GREEN Engine tools (see Figure 6 for an overview) as well as the entire process of their application during the Citizens Observatory Experiments.

Evaluation Phases:

- **Pre-Pilot** User-Centered Design (UCD) evaluations were conducted to support the development and adaptation of GREENGAGE tools using focused stakeholder feedback from pilot cities.

⁶ based on non-expert user feedback. The updated version features enhanced visual separation between modules, clear titles for each visualization component, and detailed descriptions explaining their functionality, addressing user concerns about visual clarity and comprehensibility.

- **Pilot Phase** Evaluations were integrated into piloting workshops using paper-based and online surveys (closed and open-ended). Surveys were translated into local languages where appropriate.

Participants:

For a thorough investigation of the GREEN Engine, citizens and other stakeholders were asked to fill in online surveys after using the tools. This was carried out directly after various events with citizens or by sending the surveys to the engaged Citizen Observers via email. The participants were recruited from multiple pilot cities to ensure they represented a diverse range of demographics (age, gender, education, employment status, native language, cultural background, etc.).

The feedback collected was focused on evaluating the following:

- Usability
- Suitability
- Relevance
- Effectiveness and potential benefits
- Shortcomings of GREENGAGE methods and tools

Figure 6: Different tools of the GREEN Engine ©GREENGAGE .

6 Evaluation results

This section provides results from the applied user evaluation surveys used during the Citizens Observatory Experiments. The surveys were set up on Google Forms to enable digital contributions and were translated to the local languages of the pilot regions to ensure wide-spread use and to avoid potential language barriers. In total, N=80 people filled out the survey. The following sections show the main results of the evaluation. It should be noted that during the evaluation process, the surveys were partially completed on paper. Because of this, the manually filled-in data afterwards has been integrated with the online survey. Unfortunately, participants who completed the printed surveys did not answer all the questions, as the online questionnaire indicates. As a result, in some cases different numbers of participants appear in the analysis below.

6.1 Socio-demographic statistics

As explained in section 5, effort was made to include a diverse group of people in the evaluation. Figure 7 illustrates the spatial distribution of survey participants across the five GREENGAGE pilot locations. The majority of respondents came from Bristol (BRI), accounting for 41% (N=33) of the total sample, making it the most active pilot in providing feedback. Other participants were distributed among Turano Valley (TUR) and North Brabant (NBB), ensuring representation from diverse geographic contexts. This spread highlights the project’s pan-European engagement and the inclusion of multiple local perspectives in evaluating the GREEN Engine tools. Additionally the evaluation was performed in Vienna (VIE) 19% and Spain (DEU) 10%.

Figure 7: Location of survey users.

In terms of age groups (Figure 8), the distribution indicates a concentration within the working-age population, particularly between 18 and 44 years, while the youngest and oldest age brackets are minimally represented (This is also due to the fact that because of its data collection nature and workflow the GREENGAGE app is rated 18+ and can only be used under supervision of an adult, e.g., in a school context, by underage children). The 35–44 years age group was the largest individual group, accounting for 18.8% (N=15) of survey respondents. The second-largest segment comprises individuals aged 18–24 years (16.3%; N=13), followed by 25–34 years (15%; N=12). Other age categories include 55–64 years (12.5%; N=10), 15–17 years (11.3%; N=9), and 45–54 years (10%; N=8). While the older age group of 75–84 year olds still represented 5% of responses, very old (>= 85 years) and very young people (< 12 years) were negligible.

Figure 8: Age distribution of survey users.

The distribution of work status is given in Figure 9. Overall, the distribution indicates that about half of respondents are employed (public, private sector or self-employed) and around a third is currently engaged in education, while only a small fraction is retired or not employed. The largest proportion is represented by individuals employed in the public sector, accounting for 24.1% of the total. The second-largest category consists of students, comprising 21.5%, followed by those employed in the private sector at 16.5%. Other notable segments include individuals in education (11.4%), those who prefer not to disclose their status (8.9%), and self-employed individuals (5.1%). Smaller categories include interns (3.8%), not employed (3.8%) and retired (2.5%).

Figure 9: Work status of survey users.

The overwhelming majority of respondents (N=60) stated that they have an advanced level of digital literacy (defined as “I make purchases electronically, I use spreadsheets, ...”), comprising 75.9% of the total participants (Figure 10). Five persons (6.3%) said they are digital illiterate (“zero level”, defined as “I do not use any digital tool including a smartphone”). 5% (N=4) each self-classified as “basic level” (defined as “I use WhatsApp, I browse a little through websites, ...”) or intermediate level (defined as “I browse websites, I watch videos on YouTube, ...”). 7.6% did not or could not self-classify their digital literacy. These figures indicate a strong dominance of advanced digital skills within the population, with only a small proportion reporting uncertainty or limited proficiency. Overall, the distribution suggests that digital literacy is generally high among respondents, though targeted support may be necessary for the minority with low or uncertain skill levels.

Figure 10: Digital literacy of survey users.

In terms of education level (Figure 11), the distribution indicates an over-representation of individuals with advanced degrees obtained by tertiary education. About half of respondents had a university degree: 21.5% of respondents holding a Master’s degree, 13.9% a PhD and 12.7% a Bachelor’s degree. The largest individual group was people with secondary school education, accounting for 31.6% of the total population and 16.5% had high school diplomas as their highest educational level. Primary education levels was only minimally represented by a single respondent, which might even be represented by a non-adult participant as the GREENGAGE App is rated 18+ for under age childrens’ data protection reasons.

The skewed distribution towards highly educated participants may stem from the fact, that the evaluation was part of a scientifically biased project, where high education levels are standard, and recruiting test subjects is often done in scientific environments where similar education levels prevail. Additionally, being part of citizen scientist workshops might be more attractive for people with high educational affinity. However, for achieving the GREENGAGE goals in the future, reaching out and attracting a more heterogenous citizen group will be a key in future Observatories. Nevertheless, this analysis is already demonstrating that the GREEN Engine has the capacity to signpost biases in the Observer structure which can then be tackled by the organisers of an Observatory.

Figure 11: Education level of survey users.

The gender distribution indicates a relatively balanced representation between female and male respondents (Figure 12). Women representing 52.5% (N=42) of the total participants, with 43.8% (N=35) identifying as male. Non-binary individuals and those who chose not to specify their gender were only minimally represented.

Figure 12: Gender of survey users.

6.2 Workshop activities

The evaluation surveys were filled in as part of Citizen Observatory workshops. These workshops not only included demonstrating the GREEN Engine technology, but also activities by the participants like gathering data in field tests, supervised by experts. In Figure 13 and Figure 14 we asked them about the usefulness of these activities and if those were interesting for them.

Figure 13: Usefulness of the workshop activities

The histogram in Figure 13 displays the distribution of responses regarding how useful the workshops were for the participants, where 1 indicates very low usefulness and 5 indicates very high usefulness. The mean value was 4.0, meaning most people agreed about the usefulness of the activities. The most frequent rating was 5 (very high usefulness, N=31) or 4 (high usefulness, N=22), rating that a significant majority found the activities highly beneficial. Lower ratings 2 (low usefulness, N=6) and 1 (very low usefulness, N=2) are rare, with only a handful of respondents assigning these scores, indicating minimal dissatisfaction or perceived irrelevance.

Figure 14: Interest in the workshop activities

Figure 14 shows the distribution of responses regarding how interesting the activities were perceived by the participants, where 1 indicates very low interest and 5 indicates very high interest. The mean value was 4.4, indicating that most people agreed on the usefulness of the activities. The most frequent ratings are 5 (very high interest, N=44) and 4 (high interest, N=22), indicating that the majority found the technology highly engaging. The “neutral” rating 3 accounts for 8 respondents and lower ratings (1 and 2) were the complete exception.

Interestingly, the question about the interest in the workshop activities shows even more positive scores than the questions about the usefulness of the workshops (Figure 13). An interpretation might be that doing these activities was a lot of fun, but citizen observers might not be sure if the results really lead to any changes in their neighbourhood.

We also asked participants for free-text comments to these questions and it was nice to see that the majority of users brought up that they enjoyed being part of the Citizen Observatory, and that they find it very useful. Notable comments include (minimally edited for typos or grammatical errors to improve reading while keeping the original intent):

"I enjoyed hearing about the research and the data collection methods seem democratic and empowering in a situation where I have felt completely disempowered."

"I didn't understand before I came what I was actually attending - apart from that it was about EBLN ⁷feedback. I was pleasantly surprised to find out about the app and to understand the observatory aims"

"I hope this activity offers us some way of getting our views across to council."

"Felt heard; Good that it is in-person"

"Finally felt heard. Well done, covered all."

"Seems as though it could be a useful tool."

"I am glad to have access to an organisation which appears to be prepared to objectively collect unbiased data regarding the impact of the EBLN."

This feedback clearly shows the importance of such observatories and that users want to be heard and should be included more in decision making.

⁷ EBLN East Bristol Livable Neighbourhood

6.3 GREEN Engine usage

Figure 15 and Figure 16 illustrate the distribution of responses regarding which GREEN Engine components were actively tested or at least passively consumed (e.g. by watching videos, reading documentation or watching other people use it) in the evaluation. Note that these were multiple-choice questions, so the total percentage of responses can be more than 100%.

The by far most tested part of the GREEN Engine was the GREENGAGE App which was used by over 77% (N=51) of respondents. Trailing behind were the Conversation Stations, asking about the non-technical possibilities to engage citizens in active conversations, with 18% (N=12). Some people also used the separate GREENGAGE apps like the MindView for GREENGAGE App (7.6%, N=5) and Atmotube sensors (6.1%, N=4). A better integration of these external apps and sensors within the main GREENGAGE app might drive up the usage of those technologies. Apache Superset – the back-end technology to create advanced database analytics and data visualizations – was only used by 3% (N=2) of users. This is not surprising, as – though user friendly – usage of data analytics tools still requires very advanced technical knowledge and a fair amount of time to learn the technology and data models.

This is also reflected in the findings of Figure 16, which asked for passive interaction with the GREEN Engine. Here, Apache Superset was the second most watched technology by 20% (N=9). This implies that there is interest in this part of the technology stack. A possible solution to increase the actual users of Apache Superset would be to offer hands-on workshops especially tailored towards citizen scientists who want to do data analytics. Another interpretation is to acknowledge the fact that maybe more people are interested to be citizen observers, then gathering data as citizen scientists. Doing the actual data analytics and that analysis still must be done by trained experts, though, as the project found out.

Figure 15: Which (parts of the) GREEN Engine were personally tested by the survey users.

Figure 16: Which (parts of the) GREEN Engine were watched (video tutorials, other users using them, ...) by the survey users.

The third question about the GREEN Engine was which part of the whole stack was most interesting (Figure 17). Clear leader here was, again, the GREENGAGE App which 61.2 % (N=41) found most interesting, followed by the MindViewfor GREENGAGE App which 13.4 % (N=9) found most interesting. Apache Superset (11.9 %, N=8) having similar high numbers as in the “watched” question (Figure 16). Again, this reveals that participants really liked the concept of the data analytics and visualisation part and are probably only put off from actually using it due to its technical complexity. Atmotube and Conversation Stations were least interesting. It has to be mentioned that the Conversation Station was introduced quite late as a GREEN Engine asset and was only available in the Bristol Pilot, which explains the low value in Figure 17. Nevertheless, this shows clearly that Citizen Observatories must use a combination of the best tools for the tasks, combining older and newer technologies as well as digital and analog tools to be successful.

Figure 17: Which (parts of the) GREEN Engine are most interesting for the participants.

These findings reveal the strong engagement with the GREENGAGE App and suggests that participants value the general concept of GREENGAGE and see use in a single app supporting them in their observatory. High passive exposure rates indicate that even non-active users are curious about the platform, emphasizing the importance of accessible tutorials and demonstrations. Additionally, the high interest in environmental monitoring and citizen engagement features aligns with the project’s goal of fostering participatory governance, suggesting that these areas could drive adoption and long-term impact. The relatively low interest in actively using back-end functionalities implies that future development should prioritize enhancing usability and visual analytics, while simplifying complex processes for non-technical users.

6.4 GREEN Engine usability

Figure 18 shows how participants rated the usability of the GREEN Engine on a scale from 1 (very low usability) to 5 (very high usability). Overall, the tools were perceived as usable, with a slightly positive mean score of 3.6. The most often chosen value was 3 (neutral) by 26 persons, closely followed by 4 (good usability, N=22) and 5 (very good usability, N=14). Very low usability was only chosen by 2 people, and low usability by 3 people. This shows a strong skeweness towards good usability, but also shows the fact, that most people thought the usability was “neutral” instead liking it a lot.

Figure 18: Usability Rating Distribution Analysis

These quantitative results gave a first impression how people perceived the GREENGAGE tools at the time of the survey. But in order to actually improve things, we also asked the users for additional free-text input to see what worked well and which things could be improved. Especially important was feedback what could be enhanced in the apps and in the general workflow of user engagement. It was not even important if the feedback was objectively correct or not, since, if many participants perceive the same things, it might indicate that the user experience could be improved.

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What to enhance

The following are notable comments on GREENGAGE 's usability. Most feedback brought up user interface and data handling issues:

"Connection between GREENGAGE APP and Atmotube (something native, instead manual input)"

"We could see the start and end points in the GREENGAGE app, but we couldn't see the required route."

"Aggregation function. I only get survey results per POI, but not really for the whole spatial region"

"Being able to know which tasks have been already completed"

"I would like connect the Atmotube to GREENGAGE App to send periodically the data "

"UX"

"The labels were confusing"

"I think the title Field when submitting a Spot is unnecessary and bothersome, maybe all Text fields could be optional?"

"General usability - make it more intuitive "

"Sometimes it is not clear if it is already working/tracking."

"Workflows on general, some buttons not working sometimes"

"Clearer where you enter a point (drag and drop pin); add option for points "safety issue""

"Battery was flat"

"Tracking does not stop"

"Not sure for me but really useful for me. Hard to say"

"General usability could be improved"

"Filling in demographic info multiple times is annoying"

Note that many of these things have already been fixed in the latest version of the tools as a direct result of the evaluation phase. Unfortunately, there has not yet been another evaluation survey with feedback gathered in the evaluation phase to see if the software and workflow enhancements also further improved the usability ratings.

7 Conclusions and Uptake

The evaluation results demonstrate that GREENGAGE successfully engaged diverse stakeholders and provided valuable insights into the usability and relevance of the GREEN Engine tools. While the GREENGAGE App emerged as the most widely adopted component (77% used it), the relatively low feedback of companion tools such as MindView for GREENGAGE App and Atmotube (6-7% usage respectively) highlights the need for better integration and streamlined workflows. A better integration

within the main GREENGAGE App might drive up the usage of those technologies. This could yield a higher usage rate for these tools if the workflow were more unified. Other feedback to improve the general workflow has already been implemented as part of the project, e.g. simplify forms by making some text fields optional and avoiding repeated demographic info requests.

The strong interest in workshop activities, coupled with positive feedback on their usefulness, underscores the importance of participatory approaches in fostering trust and engagement. However, the observed discrepancy between perceived interest (mean score=4.4) and perceived usefulness (mean score=4.0) suggests that future initiatives should focus on demonstrating tangible outcomes from citizen contributions, thereby reinforcing the value of participation.

Looking ahead, the uptake of GREENGAGE tools beyond the pilot phase will depend on sustained support, clear communication of benefits, and integration with local governance processes. Future projects should explore scalable models for Citizen Observatories, leveraging lessons learned from GREENGAGE to design inclusive, transparent, and impactful engagement strategies. By continuing to refine the GREEN Engine and fostering strong partnerships between citizens, researchers, and public authorities, GREENGAGE can serve as a blueprint for participatory governance in achieving the European Green Deal objectives.

Lessons learned:

The significance of iterative co-design lies in ensuring tool usability, emphasising transparent data workflows to foster trust, and advocating for modular, scalable technology to accommodate various Citizen Observatory applications.

Once deployed, tools must remain accessible, with dependable technical support readily available. Citizen Observatory tools should be simple to use for people with varying levels of technical skills. Using cloud services allows the system to expand and be utilised in many locations, but this also means ongoing costs, so reliable funding is essential. Public authorities should consider forming public-private partnerships or securing diverse funding sources to keep the tools operational. Tests in different areas show that the tools can be tailored to local needs while maintaining the core approach.

For broader use, self-paced training materials, such as video tutorials that explain how to use each tool, are essential. GREENGAGE provided extensive training materials in its [GREENGAGE Academy](#). The GREEN Engine Tools have been documented at [Github](#) and <https://docs-stage.GREENGAGE.dev/docs>.

8 References

Wernbacher, T., Pfeiffer, A., Gebetsroither-Geringer, E., Goels, M., Worster, J., Meißner, E., Graf, A., Stollnberger, R., Geyer, R., Schmidt, R.-R., & Serada, A. (2022). *HotCity—A Gamified Token System for Reporting Waste Heat Sources* (S. 15–27). https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-93780-5_2

9 Annex A

The screenshot shows the 'Issues' tab in the plan.io interface. The table lists feature requests categorized by assignee: Alejandra Lizama (MindEarth) with 2 items, Dawid Wolosiuk (VRVie) with 3 items, and Dmitry Alabyan (DigitalSunray) with 4 items. Each row includes a checkbox, ID, tracker, status, priority, subject, and update timestamp.

<input type="checkbox"/>	#	TRACKER	STATUS	PRIORITY	SUBJECT	UPDATED
Alejandra Lizama (MindEarth) 2						
<input type="checkbox"/>	753	Feature_Request	Completed	High	There needs to be a possibility to do one mission several times (--> validation mission)	2024-07-19 10:21 AM ...
<input type="checkbox"/>	774	Feature_Request	Completed	High	Icons for start and endpoint could be improved	2024-12-04 02:44 PM ...
Dawid Wolosiuk (VRVie) 3						
<input type="checkbox"/>	981	Feature_Request	Completed	High	Public Dashboards possible?	2025-05-26 10:29 AM ...
<input type="checkbox"/>	751	Feature_Request	Completed	High	Automatically bridge Greengage App data to Druid	2025-08-07 08:40 AM ...
<input type="checkbox"/>	1067	Feature_Request	Completed	High	Superset: MODE Map with different modes depicted	2025-08-14 08:57 AM ...
Dmitry Alabyan (DigitalSunray) 4						
<input type="checkbox"/>	795	Feature_Request	Completed	High	Change "City" to "Citizen Observatory" in GREENGAGE App	2024-11-20 11:24 AM ...
<input type="checkbox"/>	765	Feature_Request	Completed	High	Improve threshold for GPS recognition of the marked line	2024-11-27 03:02 PM ...
<input type="checkbox"/>	824	Feature_Request	Completed	High	Information screen at start of GREENGAGE App	2025-03-26 05:56 PM ...
<input type="checkbox"/>	908	Feature_Request	Completed	High	Change text on the Login button	2025-03-26 05:56 PM ...

Figure 19: Screenshot from plan.io, which was used to document the GREEN Engine tool development

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10 Annex B

Google FORMS Questionnaire

AWAITING VALIDATION BY THE EUROPEAN COMMISSION

GREENGAGE - Pilot Users' Demographics and Activity Satisfaction Questionnaire

* Gibt eine erforderliche Frage an

GREENGAGE (Engaging Citizens - Mobilizing Technology - Delivering the Green Deal) project has been funded by Horizon Europe programme for research, technological development and demonstration, under grant agreement No 101086530. For more information about the project, please visit: <https://www.greengage-project.eu/>

Consent and demographic data check

Please provide some background information about you.

If you fill this survey on paper (not online) then skip the following part with the GREENGAGE ID. If you already have registered then please add your GREENGAGE ID below.

- 1.1 Indicate your GREENGAGE's unique ID - get your ID at <https://me.greengage-project.eu/> (copy it clicking right hand side icon after your name)

Consent form GREENGAGE

All the information that we collect about you during the course of the research will be kept strictly confidential. You will not be able to be identified in any publications. The results of this investigation may be published in reports, scientific journals or conferences and used in further studies, but it will not be possible to identify the source of the information. Nothing of the provided data will be handed out to third parties. The authorization for the use and access to your information is valid until the end of the project, unless you decide to cancel it before. Your decision whether or not to give your authorization for the use and diffusion of the information provided by you is completely voluntary.

Regarding *my participation*, or the *participation of a minor I represent*, in the project, I declare that:

- I have been informed that GREENGAGE project is a research project currently run under the Horizon Europe Framework Programme under the grant agreement no. 101086530. The co-ordinator of the project is AIT (AUSTRIAN INSTITUTE OF TECHNOLOGY GMBH). The coordinator of the project may be contacted at contact@greengage-project.eu. The coordinator of this study may be contacted with regard to any question about my participation at contact@greengage-project.eu.
 - I have read and understood the Research Ethics Protocol for GREENGAGE Citizen Scientists and I abide by its principles.
 - I have been informed about the purposes of the project and I have fully understood which tasks my participation in the study entails from my side. I had enough time to think and I have been able to ask all the questions that have come to mind and I have received a clear answer to those questions.
 - [I have fully understood that my participation is entirely voluntary and that I can withdraw at any time without any detrimental consequences.](#)
 - [I understand I will not be paid for my participation.](#)
 - [I understand the risks that my participation to this research may carry.](#)
 - [I understand that if I choose to withdraw from the project, I am obliged to return all the technology and tools I have received from the GREENGAGE partners.](#)
 - [I understand the benefits that my participation to this research entails.](#)
2. 1.2 I accept the above written consent form. If you don't accept then we can not use the feedback. *

Markieren Sie nur ein Oval.

Yes *Fahren Sie mit Frage 3 fort*

No *Wechseln Sie zu Abschnitt 5 (Thank you very much for your time!)*

Some questions about you

We will be pleased if you complete the following anonymous questions, allowing us knowing the profile of pilot's participants.

3. 3.1 In what role do you play in GREENGAGE in thematic co-explorations *

Check as many options as you feel suit.

Wählen Sie alle zutreffenden Antworten aus.

- Participant – active participant in a thematic co-exploration team
- Core team member- organizer and knowledge leader of a thematic co-exploration
- Pilot owner - promoter of a thematic co-exploration in a domain
- Citizenry - target for dissemination and communication of results of a thematic co-exploration
- Stakeholder - sponsor and receiver of results of a thematic co-exploration

4. 3.2 What is your age? *

Markieren Sie nur ein Oval.

- 12-14 years – Minors, early adolescents
- 15-17 years – Minors, late adolescents
- 18–24 years – Young adults, university-age
- 25-34 years – Early adulthood
- 35–44 years – Mid-adulthood
- 45–54 years – Late adulthood
- 55–64 years – Pre-retirement or early senior years
- 65–74 years – Early retirement
- 75–84 years – Senior adults
- Over 85 – Elderly/advanced age

5. 3.3 Gender *

Markieren Sie nur ein Oval.

- Female
- Male
- Not binary

6. 3.4 What is your level of education? *

Markieren Sie nur ein Oval.

- Secondary school
- High school diploma
- Vocational training
- Bachelor degree
- Master's degree
- PhD

7. 3.5 What is your level of knowledge in the usage of digital tools? *

Markieren Sie nur ein Oval.

- Zero level (I do not use any digital tool including a smartphone)
- Basic level (I use WhatsApp, I browse a little through websites, ...)
- Intermediate level (I browse websites, I watch videos on YouTube, ...)
- Advanced level (I make purchases electronically, I use spreadsheets, ...)

8. 3.6 Could you indicate your work status? *

Markieren Sie nur ein Oval.

- Unemployed
- Self-employed
- Employed (private sector)
- Employed (public sector)
- Retired
- Student
- Sonstiges: _____

9. 3.7 Please, select the type of stakeholder you represent *

Markieren Sie nur ein Oval.

- Citizen
- Public servant
- Non-profit organization
- For-profit organization

10. 3.8 Do you belong to a disadvantaged group: ethnic, gender, economic, social, or other? *

Markieren Sie nur ein Oval.

- Yes
 No
 I do not want to answer

Some questions about the activity (satisfaction)

11. 4.1 I think this activity was interesting to me *

Markieren Sie nur ein Oval.

1 2 3 4 5

Stro Strongly agree

12. 4.2 I think this activity was useful to me *

Markieren Sie nur ein Oval.

1 2 3 4 5

Stro Strongly agree

13. 4.3 I think that this activity dealt with an important topic to me *

Markieren Sie nur ein Oval.

1 2 3 4 5

Stro Strongly agree

14. 4.4 Comments or recommendations regarding this activity that you would like to share

Some questions regarding the GREENE ENGINE digital tools

Please give us your feedback if you had the chance to test the digital tools GREENGAGE provides as the GREENGAGE App, the MindView App, or Atmotube. If you participated in some session which explained the tools your feedback is also very helpfull and will be asked for in this section.

15. Which GREEN Engine Technology did you test yourself? *

Wählen Sie alle zutreffenden Antworten aus.

- GREENGAGE App
- MindView (MindEarth) App
- Atmotube
- Superset
- Editor
- I could not test any of them

16. How was the USABILITY of the Technology? *

Markieren Sie nur ein Oval.

1 2 3 4 5

very very high

17. What would you enhance?

18. Which Green Engine Technology could you watch, but not have a personal hands-on experience? *

Wählen Sie alle zutreffenden Antworten aus.

- GREENGAGE App
- MindView (MindEarth) App
- Atmotube
- Superset
- Editor
- Sonstiges: _____

19. Which technology is interesting to you? *

Wählen Sie alle zutreffenden Antworten aus.

- GREENGAGE App
- MindView (MindEarth) App
- Atmotube
- Superset
- Editor

20. Which kind of technology/feature is missing?

Thank you very much for your time!

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